

ISic0460

I.Sicily inscription 0460

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Tuuli Ahlholm,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico

Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 258 + 266 + 282

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Iul(iae) innocenti
2. in pacae. vixi[t]
3. annos III, m[en]
4. ses VIII, dies VI,
5. oras diei X
6. f(ecerunt) innocen[ti][---]

Apparatus

Text of Agnello 1953

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491688

EDCS 21900527

Bibliography

Mommsen, Th. 1883. *Inscriptiones Bruttiorum Lucaniae Campaniae Siciliae Sardiniae Latinae. Pars posterior. Inscriptiones Siciliae et Sardiniae. Corpus Inscriptionum Latinarum, consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae editum.* Berlin. At 10.7182 +

10.7186 (<http://arachne.uni-koeln.de/item/buchseite/650770>)

Agnello, S.L. 1953. *Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia.* Rome. At no.83

Ferrua, A 1946-1947. *Florilegio d'iscrizioni paleocristiane di Sicilia. Rendiconti della Pontifica accademia romana di archeologia.* 22: 227-239. At 232 no.12

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-17): ISic0460. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4337515>